

Service Quality Assessment Of Selected Heritage Sites Incambodia, Indonesia, And Philippines By Tourists Towards The Development Of Service Delivery Improvement Plan

Mary Grace H. Laserna

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Abstract

Tourists are attracted to travelling to the historic places. The Heritage sites of Angkor in Cambodia, Borobudur Temple Compound in Indonesia and Historic City of Vigan in the Philippines are a mixture of heritage attractions and culture that correspond to its status as UNESCO World Heritage Sites. Tourism in these places has experienced continued growth and development. Today it has become a great challenge to sustain and satisfy the needs and demands of tourists when it comes to service quality.

The main objective of this study is to critically assess the service quality of tourism facilities and services based on the expectation, perceived performance, level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention. Data were collected by use of re-modified SERVQUAL model into a new model called HISTOQUAL relevant to historical sites through five dimensions of responsiveness, tangible, empathy, communications and consumables to Filipino tourists residing in the Philippines who have visited at least one (1) from selected heritage sites in Cambodia, Indonesia, and Philippines.

The findings showed mostly, a significant difference between the perception of tourist on the expectation and perceived performance based on service quality dimensions in Angkor (responsiveness, tangible, empathy, and communication), Borobudur (tangible and communications) and Vigan (responsiveness, tangible, empathy and communications). On the other hand, in terms of profile of the respondents, there was a significant difference on expectation for number of countries visited (empathy in Borobudur), sex (responsiveness, empathy and consumable in Angkor while empathy in Vigan), highest educational attainment (communication in Angkor) and for main purpose of visit (empathy in Vigan while communication and consumables in Angkor). While, on perceived performance for place visited (communication and consumables in all selected heritage sites), civil status (responsiveness, empathy and communication in Angkor while responsiveness and consumables in Borobudur). Furthermore, the study revealed that respondents were satisfied in terms of overall service quality in all selected heritage sites. They also agreed to visit again, willing to recommend to their family and friends and be able to stay longer. Finally, the study revealed that consumables (Angkor), communication (Borobudur) and consumable and empathy (Vigan) were the strongest predictor of the overall satisfaction. Furthermore, communication (Angkor), tangible (Borobudur) and responsiveness (Vigan) were the factors that affects the overall revisit intentions of respondents. The paper recommends that tourist should be given customer satisfaction survey, update heritage staffs and tour guides through seminars, conferences and workshops. Furthermore, improve facilities, equipment, and provide enough information. Finally, intensify the good relationship among residents, local government, tourism officers, stakeholders, academe and other government sectors and possible implementation of proposed service delivery improvement plan.

Introduction

Heritage tourism is a fast growing and improving niche market. It comprises appreciating and visiting historical or industrial sites that may include old canals, railways, battlegrounds, military sites, etc. which general purpose is to understand and appreciate the significance of the past. This type of market is powered by an expanding number of tourists. Travel industry has developed a substantial "new" region of the travel industry request because people desire and long to look for something new and bizarre, including that of customary culture. Heritage tourism is currently a significant travel industry technique of many countries. In different countries, they share in common regarding heritage tourism strategies used to boost local culture, and that they can aid the occasional and geographic spread of travel industry (Richards, 1995).

One of the largest industries nowadays in the world is tourism industry, and despite recent events that have made its operating environment more complex, it continues to grow (Theobald, 2005). This has been acknowledged not only in developed countries but in developing countries as well. Tourism pertains to different activities resulting from visitors' interactions with their destination. This activity includes using and buying of stuff, transportation, accommodation, cards, railways, tickets, clothes, souvenirs, delivery services, food, electronic gadgets, travel insurance, and package tours paid by people who visit a destination that provide physical and psychological satisfaction. Through tourism activities, the livelihood of the community is improved at the same time while impacting the economic development positively. Also, according to Ardahaey (2010), tourism industry distinguish as a valuable agent for expansion and improvement in almost all sectors of the economy, such as Trade and Industry, education, culture, entertainment, infrastructure, health, business, construction, transportation, communication, social services, and natural resources. Ashley (2015) presented that despite turbulent phase for the world's economy, tourism remains the economic driver of that spice up 'the livelihood of the common people. Focusing the wealth creating power of tourism on people most in need remains an immense task and opportunity.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 1972) set up the World Heritage Convention with the goal to distinguish, identify, ensure and rejoice the worlds natural characteristic and outstanding cultural heritage sites. World Heritage signifies remarkable places that are vital part of travel industry and have a special significance for humanity. The destinations that enter the World Heritage List are secured by law and are economically supported by the World Heritage Fund.

So as to be chosen, according to Jokilehto et al. (2008) explained that properties should be a universal value beyond the national boundaries and meet the choice standards set by UNESCO. For instance, the identified site for cultural heritage need to symbolize an extraordinary human accomplishment, vital stage in history or noteworthy living convention. In the same way, the nominated site for natural heritage values needs to hold exceptional common magnificence and provide an evidence of valuable living space for endangered species. At the point when a site gets listed as a World Heritage property it demonstrates to be extraordinarily useful not only for the nation in which it is found, yet likewise for the local population and the visitors. A portion of the advantages incorporate: International recognition that brings incredible national pride, greater tourist inflow, growth in employment openings for the resident and enhanced development and infrastructural facilities in the area.

Angkor in Cambodia, Borobudur Temple Compounds in Indonesia and Historic Town of Vigan in the Philippines are considered as ancient monuments recorded in the World Heritage Lists.

Angkor in Cambodia incorporated all major architectural structures and hydrological engineering systems from the Khmer time and a large portion of these reservoirs and waterways still exist today (Kausar, 2009). In addition, the author noted that the best-preserved architectural masterpiece from the Khmer kingdom which ruled a large swath of Indochina from the 7th to the 12th century.

Borobudur Temple Compounds in Indonesia was a center for Buddhist worship till at some point between the tenth and fifteenth hundreds of years when it was relinquished (Kausar, 2009). The information explained that it was rediscovered in the nineteenth century and reestablished in the twentieth century, and now attracts a bigger number of vacationers than Buddhist explorers who come to admire its architectural symmetry in the midst of a serene, forested landscape.

Historic Town of Vigan in the Philippines denotes a one-of-a-kind combination of Asian structure design and development with European colonial architecture and planning (Villalon, 1999). The study discussed that this site is a well-preserved and exceptionally intact example of Spanish colonial town planning.

Service quality is considered as a standard used to evaluate the effectiveness of travel industry administration sector and recreational package deal agency (Godbey, 1997), and therefore the excellence of service involved with tourism assumes a significant role during the time of delivery (Wyllie, 2000). Further, the quality-of-service affect customers' image on the process from expected quality to perceived quality (Prabaharan et al., 2008). Customer satisfaction can also be defined as satisfaction based on an outcome or a process (Vavra, 1997). This leads to more repeated visits and greater sales revenue (Eraqi, 2006). This enables serving staff on performance-related

pay to earn more and enhance the quality of their service to the customer. According to Glatzer (2000), the extra profit generated enables tourism enterprise/destination management to invest in upgrading facilities to the customer and in training schemes beside creating innovative business environment for tourism services improvement. Happiness is clearly distinguished to fulfillment, and generally speaking the overall happiness in recreation travel sector (Glatzer, 2000) where most of the tourists have encountered unforgettable experiences with destinations, and their observations are encountered by assessments among attractions, services, and administration measures (Laws, 1995).

Tourism Services

Tourism related services encompasses services provided by travel agencies, airlines, hotels and restaurants (including catering), and tour operator services, tourist guide services and other related services wherein it provides a lot of advantage to different hospitality services in terms of accommodations, including entertainment, hotels and resorts; transportation services, such as taxis, trains, air lines, cruise ships; and venues such as parks, museum, temples, churches, zoos, heritage and cultural sites and theatres (WTO, 1985). In a study done by Medlik & Middleton (1973), tourist product is considered as the three primary parts of attractions, facilities at the destination and accessibility of the destination. In addition, Middleton & Clarke (2001) presented that there are five principle segments in the general item, specifically: attractions and condition of environment, facilities and services, accessibility, image, and price.

Service Quality

Service quality has become an important part of research because of its relationship to costs (Crosby, 1979), profitability (Buzzell, & Gale, 1987); customer satisfaction (Bolton & Drew, 1991) and customer retention (Reichheld & Sasser, 1990). Service quality is characterized as what the client gets out and is happy to avail for "instead of" what the provider places in (Ducker, 1991). The study of Zeithaml et al. (1996) has hypothesized service quality as the general impression of clients towards the administration shortcoming or matchless quality. Thus, service quality commonly has been theorized as the contrast between the perceived services expected performance and perceived service actual performance (Bloemer et al., 1999). As revealed in the study of Parasuraman et al. (1985) that service quality is directed on tourist revisit and development of tourism industry with regards to five dimensions of service quality. They are Tangibles (physical facilities in terms of appearance, personnel and materials), Assurance (knowledge and courtesy of employees), Responsiveness (willingness to help customers and the promptness of service), and Empathy (caring and individualized attention to customers) and Reliability (dependable and accurate performance).

Customer Satisfaction

In the travel industry, satisfaction of customer is the guest's condition of feeling after they experience the tour (Baker & Crompton, 2000; Sanchez et al., 2006). Customer satisfaction is one the most areas being looked into in numerous travel industry concentrates because of its significance in defining the accomplishments and continued presence of the travel industry business (Gursoy et al., 2007). Customer satisfaction is a very important part of the business setup because business generates much revenue from the industry when the customer is satisfied by the services being provided (Deng et al., 2009). A particular of theory that has a significant influence on tourist satisfaction is the Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory. The expectancy-disconfirmation model was introduced by Oliver (1981) for studies of customer satisfaction in the retail and service industry. Expectancy-disconfirmation theory suggests that customers form their satisfaction with a target product or service as a result of subjective (or direct) comparisons between their expectations and perceptions. Expectancy-disconfirmation model measures the satisfaction of customer from the contrast between expectation and experience in perceived products or services.

A. Responsiveness

Parasuraman et al. (1985) highlighted that responsiveness is the willingness and readiness to help clients by offering prompt assistance with proper timeliness. Thus, service staff needs to be mindful on customers' needs, queries and complaints. The ability of employees to offer the necessary service without any inconvenience will have an impact on customer satisfaction. Also, in the recent study of Pakurar et al. (2019), discussed that responsiveness is primarily concerned about how administration firms react to clients by means of their personnel. Individual consideration will increase the customer's satisfaction. Armstrong (2012) explained that eagerness to assist clients and offer quick service is known as responsiveness. Also, Iqbal et al. (2010) pointed out that providing service in a timely manner is highly appreciated by customers.

B. Tangible

Tangible resources are physical artefacts that are considered necessary to be preserved for the benefit of future generations. In addition, monuments, historic places and building can be defined as tangible immovable resources whereas objects in museum belong to tangible movable resources (UNESCO). According to Parasuraman et al. (1985), tangibles as a dimension allude to service quality which emphasizes on the characteristics that signify the

service physically, i.e., where the product or service is not only seen but also satisfactorily workable or useable. It is related with the physical facilities, communications, equipment, materials and machines in order to offer the service. Parasuraman et al. (1991) refers to the presence of equipment, physical facilities, written materials and work force which are furthermore essential causing customer to feel enchanted and develop ownership towards the organization's brand image. Pakurár et al. (2019) discussed the clear visibility of resources essential for offering a support to clients, the presence of the management team and expert representatives, brochures and booklets, which will affect customer satisfaction comprise the dimension of tangibles.

C. Empathy

Empathy is the service quality which centers around managing customers as individuals (Parasuraman et al., 1985). They added that customers need to feel they are made priority by the association offering types of assistance. Service providers must be able to put themselves in the shoes of the customers to enable them to better understand the latter's needs. It implies caring, giving individual consideration, and offering types of assistance to customers. It is conveying the feeling that the customer is unique and exceptional. In doing so, the service providers can provide satisfaction to the customers. As stated in Mmutle&Shonhe (2017), individualized service denotes caring and recognizing customers' requests and desires. If the customers indicate poor performance, the tendency is they would not recommend the place to anyone. Poor customer satisfaction can result to lost business. Therefore, service employees need to meet the expectations and recognize the needs and wants to have a good feedback and positive recommendations from clients.

D. Communication

The role of communication has important implications theoretically and managerially in the services industry (Allwood, 1995). The author added that in order for communication to occur, a shared willingness and rationality must exist for successful verbal and non-verbal communication exchanges. Also, according to Parasuraman et al. (1988), the information that is transmitted to the customer plays a critical role in the service encounter. When information is incomplete or incorrect, severe inconsistencies can arise and affect the service quality perceptions. Czepial et al. (1985) stated that by recognizing the importance of personal and impersonal communications, organizations are in a more effective position to prepare, control and correct any discrepancies that may arise. This ability can link expectations and reality and prevent unsatisfactory performance. A recent study by Mmutle&Shonhe (2017) also found that communication implies guaranteed good impact on service operations and management policies. Therefore, it is necessary to communicate with the customer with accuracy and not misleading information and ensure standard of supervision and reputation to meet customers' expectations through feedback measurement.

E. Consumables

The study of Kotler & Turner (1989) defined the term 'product' in showcasing theory is characterized as whatever can be offered to a business opportunity for attention, acquisition, use of consumption that might satisfy a need or want. Lewis (1984) puts an emphasis on satisfying customer needs. Customer wants and needs should be satisfied by marketing offerings such as products, services, and experience. Richards & Munsters (2010) added that in order to attract more tourist, cultural tourism providers always position their products uniquely which involves cultural tourism destination, cultural environment or cultural events by focusing on their core cultural element. According to the study of Olalere (2017), tourist avail or buy souvenirs and services during their vacation because this is one of the prevalent elements why they travel to other places. The findings show that tourist purchase different souvenirs because every item is a representation to remind them of their travel experiences, memories, and identities.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the service quality of tourism facilities and services in selected heritage sites, namely, Angkor Wat in Cambodia, Borobudur Compound Temple in Indonesia and the Historic City of Vigan in the Philippines.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Place visited;
 - 1.2. Number of countries visited;
 - 1.3. Age;
 - 1.4. Sex;
 - 1.5. Civil Status;
 - 1.6. Highest Educational Attainment; and,
 - 1.7. Main Purpose of Visit?

2. What is the perception of the respondents on the expectation and perceived performance of respondents on service quality assessment of selected heritage sites from Cambodia, Indonesia and Philippines with respect to:
 - 2.1. Responsiveness;
 - 2.2. Tangible;
 - 2.3. Empathy;
 - 2.4. Communications; and,
 - 2.5. Consumables?
3. How do the assessment on the expectation and perceived performance of service quality in the selected heritage sites compare, as to:
 - 3.1. Quality Dimensions; and,
 - 3.2. Profile of the respondents?
4. How do the level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention compare when grouped according to demographic profile?
5. Which among the quality dimensions of service quality are determinants of the overall satisfaction and revisit intention in the selected heritage sites from Cambodia, Indonesia and Philippines?
6. What service delivery improvement plan can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be of utmost importance to the following:

1. The residents of the areas considered under study will become more aware and conscious of the heritage sites in their country and can contribute to the protection and preservation of these UNESCO World Heritage Sites.
2. Tourists who are interested to visit heritage sites may be encouraged to be responsible tourists and value, conserve and exercise sustainable tourism practices while supporting the well-being of the local people.
3. Travel Agents and tour guides will gain insights on how to promote and cater the Heritage Sites of the said countries.
4. National Tourism Organization will develop insights on how to improve the tourism facilities and services in UNESCO World Heritage Sites.
5. National Government will be provided with new ideas and information on how to improve the delivery of tourism services in the Heritage Sites.
6. Lastly, Other Researchers will develop insights on how to improve the tourism facilities and services in heritage sites and can conduct further research on the implications of the study.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design through the conduct of a quantitative survey method to know the service quality assessment of Selected Heritage Sites in Cambodia, Indonesia and the Philippines. According to Best (2007), descriptive method involves description, records, investigations, and interpretation of existing conditions.

Setting of the Study

The study was conducted on three of the UNESCO World Heritage Sites, namely, Angkor in Cambodia, Borobudur Temple Compounds in Indonesia, and Historic City of Vigan in the Philippines.

Subjects/ Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were Filipino tourists residing in the Philippines who visited the selected heritage sites, namely, Angkor in Cambodia, Borobudur Compound Temple in Indonesia and the Historic City of Vigan in the Philippines from year 2018 to 2020. The respondents were elementary and secondary teachers, tourism officers, tourism personnel, tour group participants, tour operators, tour guides, and graduate students.

Sample size and Sampling Technique

A total of four hundred (400) survey questionnaires was carried out by directly distributing questionnaire to the respondents who agreed to participate in the survey.

The sample size was derived through Cochran's formula by computing the minimum sample size required for accuracy in estimating proportions by considering the standard normal deviation set at 95% confidence level (1.96), percentage of response (50% = 0.5) with the confidence interval of $0.05 = \pm 5$.

Then, the researcher determined the fully completed questionnaires to be included in the study. However, there were 271 incomplete data and unanswered survey questionnaire because most of them did not visit the said heritage sites. Due to an unexpected change of public health emergency because of a pandemic, an online survey

was carried out to address the concern. A total of 268 people participated in the online survey. Yet, a total of 220 surveys was considered usable.

There were 300 respondents chosen out of 349 Filipino respondents. The researcher computed the minimum sample size by considering the standard normal deviation set at 95% confidence level (1.96) with the quantifying sampling error of ± 5.6 with the total number of populations of 300.

The researcher employed Simple Random Sampling in selecting sample through the process of lottery method to avoid bias. The researcher assigned every paper with a unique number. These numbers were put in a jar and thoroughly mixed. After that, the researcher picked 49 numbers without looking at it and those numbers in papers were not included in the study. It is a process of selecting a sample that allows individual to have an equal and independent chance of being selected for the sample.

The respondents' data were gathered from different places of the Philippines from Abra, Bacolod, Batangas, Bicol, Bulacan, Cagayan, Capiz, Cavite, Cebu, Davao, Ilocos, Iloilo, Isabela, Manila, Marikina, Pangasinan, Surigao Del Sur, Quezon, Rizal, and Samar through offline and online survey in Google form.

Research Instruments

The survey questionnaire instrument is used for this study which consist of four (4) parts to assess the service quality from re-modified SERVQUAL into a new type of questionnaire called HISTOQUAL with five dimensions relevant to the heritage sites.

The first part refers to the respondents' information or the demographic profile. It consists of factual questions to describe the respondents. In this part, there would be 7 questions related to the visitors' profile such as place visited, number of countries visited, age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, and main purpose of the visit.

The second part of the questionnaire is about the perception of respondents on the expectation and perceived performance of the service quality assessment of selected heritage sites, namely, Angkor Wat in Cambodia, Borobudur Compound Temple in Indonesia and the Historic City of Vigan in the Philippines by Filipino tourists with respect to responsiveness, tangible, empathy, communications and consumables. It consists of 32 item questions from 5 dimensions of modified HISTOQUAL model. Four-point Likert scale, ranging from "Very Low Expectation" (1) to "Very High Expectation" (4) was used in order to assess the perception of respondents on the expectation and perceived performance as "Not Evident" (1) to "Very Evident" (4).

The third part refers to the overall tourist satisfactions of Filipino tourist respondents where Four-point Likert scale, ranging from "Very Dissatisfied" (1) to "Very Satisfied" (4) was used.

And lastly, Four-point Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" (1) to "Strongly Agree" (4) was utilized to assess the revisit intention of Filipino tourist respondents.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Expectancy-Disconfirmation Theory that focuses on identifying the heritage sites attribute which impact tourists' satisfaction. Expectancy-disconfirmation theory comprises of two sub-processes having independent effects on customer satisfaction: the development of expectations and the disconfirmation of those expectations through performance comparisons (Oliver, 1980). Consumer satisfaction is viewed as the result of the comparison of the perceived performance to prior expectations (Clemons & Woodruff,1992).

Theoretical Framework: Expectancy-Disconfirmation Theory

This research also emphasized the theory of service quality refers to SERVQUAL model which measures consumers perceptions of service quality with a multiple-scale items known as the SERVQUAL five dimensions; reliability, assurance, tangible, empathy and responsiveness (Parasuraman et al.,1985).

In order to measure service quality in a heritage context, Frochot & Hughes (2000) develop a new scale a model called HISTOQUAL by taking the advantage of SERVQUAL model. The authors claim that it needs to be revised according to new service areas in order to suit better new services' contexts and identifies a new scale, which assesses service quality provided in heritage sites. According to them that the HISTOQUAL scale employs a more standardized questionnaire survey and suitable for assessing the service quality performance of a property and across different heritage attractions. Three of which were developed in the original SERVQUAL model (responsiveness, tangibles and empathy) plus two new ones specific to HISTOQUAL: Communications and consumables. The authors explained that responsiveness is in relation to staff productivity and capability to distinguish customers need. Tangibles show different property environment (interior and exterior) which includes cleanliness, authenticity, and attractiveness. Communication defines the quality and how information provided to customers. Consumables is defined to additional services such as restaurants and shops. Empathy is described as the readiness to take into consideration to the needs of less able customers and children.

Conceptual Framework

As Figure 2 shows, the flow of this study can be presented in the diagrammatic format showing the different tourism facilities and services in selected heritage sites measuring the service quality from re-modified SERVQUAL model into a new model called HISTOQUAL through five dimensions of responsiveness, tangible, empathy, communications and consumables.

This is to determine the satisfaction level with a service quality by comparing destination to expectations, perceived performance and examine the disconfirmation of customer 's which may affect the overall satisfaction in order to gain an in-dept understanding and know the revisit intention of Filipino tourist.

The overall result of this study develops a service delivery improvement plan to improve the service quality in selected heritage sites, namely, Angkor Wat in Cambodia, Borobudur Compound Temple in Indonesia and the Historic City of Vigan in the Philippines.

Based on the collected data, the following are the results of the study:

1. Profile of the Respondents

Based on the profile, majority of respondents visited Historic City of Vigan, Philippines (64.33 %), followed by Angkor, Cambodia (26%) and the lowest was Borobudur Temple Compounds, Indonesia (21%). The highest proportion of the respondents who visited other countries (90.99%) fell into the bracket of 0-5. Most of them are in range of 21-30 years of age (49.34%), gender distribution were 65.67% female and 34.33% male, single (61%), Highest Educational Attainment at bachelor's degree (59.67%), Graduate or Professional Degree (25.33%), Secondary Graduate (14.33%) and Elementary Graduate (0.67). The main purpose of the visit belonged from appreciation of history/ historical interest (32%).

2. Perception on the expectation and perceived performance of the service quality assessment of selected heritage sites by tourists is as follows:

2.1. The perception of respondents with respect to responsiveness on the expectation in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.51; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.55 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.62. On the other hand, Perceived Performance in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.417; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.474 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.506. The overall mean scores on the expectation were higher than perceived performance based on the perception of the respondents.

2.2. The perception of respondents with respect to tangible on the expectation in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.633; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.538 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.56. On the other hand, Perceived Performance in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.425; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.429 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.481. The overall mean scores on the expectation were higher than perceived performance based on the perception of the respondents.

2.3. The perception of respondents with respect to empathy on the expectation in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.54; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.481 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.51. On the other hand, Perceived Performance in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.370; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.41 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.40. The overall mean scores on the expectation were higher than perceived performance based on the perception of the respondents.

2.4. The perception of respondents with respect to communication on the expectation in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.53; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.449 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.67. On the other hand, Perceived Performance in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.405; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.350 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.495. The overall mean scores on the expectation were higher than perceived performance based on the perception of the respondents.

2.5. The perception of respondents with respect to consumables on the expectation in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.510; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.500 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.60. On the other hand, Perceived Performance in Angkor, Cambodia had an overall mean score of 3.442; Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia 3.43 and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines 3.577. The overall mean scores on the expectation were higher than perceived performance based on the perception of the respondents.

3. Significant difference between the expectation and perceived performance of the service quality assessment with respect to:

3.1. Quality Dimensions

A significant difference between the perception of respondents on the expectation and perceived performance based on service quality dimensions in Angkor, Cambodia with respect to responsiveness ($P = 0.034$), tangible ($P = 0.005$), empathy ($P = 0.030$), communication ($P = 0.010$); Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia with respect to tangible ($P = 0.005$) and Communications ($P = 0.025$); And Historic City of Vigan, Philippines in terms of responsiveness ($P = 0.000$, tangible ($P = 0.005$), empathy ($P = 0.004$) and communications ($P = 0.006$).

3.2. Profile of the Respondents

3.2.1. For place visited, there is no significant difference on the perception of respondents on the expectation. It was further indicated that communication ($P = 0.026$) and consumables ($P = 0.008$) had a significant difference on perceived performance.

- 3.2.2. For number of countries visited, empathy ($P = 0.014$) in Borobudur had a significant difference on the perception of respondents on the expectation. While perceived performance in all selected heritage sites had no significant difference.
 - 3.2.3. For age, there is no significant difference on the expectation and perceived performance of the service quality assessment in all selected heritage sites.
 - 3.2.4. For sex, a significant difference on the expectation of responsiveness ($P = 0.015$), empathy ($P = 0.006$) and consumable ($P = 0.025$) in Angkor while empathy ($P = 0.012$) in Vigan. On the other hand, perceived performance in all selected heritage sites had no significant difference.
 - 3.2.5. For civil status, there is no significant difference on expectation with respect to all service quality dimensions in all selected heritage sites. On the other hand, a significant difference on perceived performance of responsiveness ($P = 0.047$), empathy ($P = 0.004$), communication ($P = 0.034$), in Angkor while responsiveness ($P = 0.014$) and consumables ($P = 0.017$) in Borobudur.
 - 3.2.6. For highest educational attainment, a significant difference on the expectation for communication ($P = 0.017$) in Angkor. On the other hand, no significant difference on perceived performance in all selected heritage sites.
 - 3.2.7. And lastly for main purpose of visit, there is a significant difference on expectation of empathy ($P = 0.004$) in Vigan while communication ($P = 0.017$) and consumables ($P = 0.007$) in Angkor. On the other hand, no significant difference on perceived performance in all selected heritage sites.
4. The level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention of tourist respondents and significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention when grouped according to their profile.
 - 4.1. All selected heritage sites were assessed by respondents as satisfactory (S) on the level of overall satisfaction. In terms of revisit intentions, Angkor, Cambodia and Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia were evaluated as agree (A). However, Revisit Intention 1 and 2 in Historic City of Vigan, Philippines were rated as strongly agree (SA) while Revisit Intention 3 was assessed as agree (A).
 - 4.2. Significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention.
 - 4.2.1. For place visited, there is no significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction ($P = 0.074$). There is a significant difference on revisit intention 1 ($P = 0.002$), revisit intention 2 ($P = 0.001$), and revisit intention 3 ($P = 0.000$) in all selected heritage sites.
 - 4.2.2. For number of countries visited, there is no significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention in all selected heritage sites.
 - 4.2.3. For age, there is no significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention in all selected heritage sites.
 - 4.2.4. For sex, there is no significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention in all selected heritage sites.
 - 4.2.5. For civil status, there is no significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction in all selected heritage sites. There is a significant difference on revisit intention 3 in Angkor ($P = 0.019$).
 - 4.2.6. For highest educational attainment, there is no significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction in all selected heritage sites. There is a significant difference on revisit intention 3 in Angkor ($P = 0.046$).
 - 4.2.7. For main purpose of visit, there is no significant difference on the level of overall satisfaction and revisit intention in all selected heritage sites.
5. Service quality dimensions that affect the Overall Satisfaction Level and revisit intention.

The factors that affect the overall satisfaction level in Angkor, Cambodia was consumables, Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia was communication and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines was consumables and empathy. On the other hand, the overall service quality dimension that affects the revisit intention in Angkor, Cambodia was communication, Borobudur Temple Compound, Indonesia was tangible and Historic City of Vigan, Philippines was responsiveness.

Conclusions

In accordance with the findings of this study, the researcher came up with the conclusions discussed below:

1. Different socio-demographic profiles, travel behavior and preferences were identified in the study, which can help heritage site planners and managers increase the attractiveness of cultural destinations, provide appealing products and use promotional strategies to better suit the market.
2. The development of service quality dimensions cannot be handpicked, nor can the different dimensions be isolated from each other, as all together they have an impact on the satisfaction of tourists. This is evident among the three heritage sites.

3. The significant difference between expectation and perceived performance of tourists in the heritage sites highlighted the importance of having a clear understanding of tourists' expectation in order to provide better facilities and services. Heritage staff and the service they provide vital elements to the overall tourist experience.
4. Heritage sites play an important role in a country's tourism industry, regardless of their tourists' profile or motivation to travel. They remain as major tourist attractions, which can make anyone's vacation a pleasurable experience. However, prioritizing the most important areas to offer better and improved service quality and to make vacation memorable remains a challenge.
5. Consumables, communication and empathy are strong predictors of overall satisfaction. Communication, tangible and responsiveness affect the overall revisit intentions of respondents. These are important factors to consider attracting not only new but repeat tourists as well.
6. The proposed service delivery improvement plan, crafted after a thorough analysis of the results of the study, is intended to address gaps in product and service delivery and help improve the overall service quality of the heritage sites.

Recommendations:

The bases of the recommendation are the established assessments of Filipino Tourists from Selected Heritage Sites in Cambodia, Indonesia, and Philippines based on Service Quality dimensions as provided in the framework of the study. In accordance with the result of this study, the researchers came up with the recommendations discussed below.

1. The tourist should be given customer satisfaction survey in which, the result can be used as a baseline for determining the level of satisfaction on the service quality for the better acquisition of service.
2. There is a need for heritage staffs and tour guides to update themselves through seminars, conferences and workshops that will enhance the knowledge and awareness of service quality in heritages sites.
3. The management should make every effort to secure facilities, equipment, updated information boards, maps, guides and the like necessary for improving the service quality for tourist.
4. The residents, local government, tourism officers, stakeholders, academe and other government sectors should intensify the good relationship and seriously discuss with intensifying different problems, issues and concerns. Otherwise, possible degradation and damage to the image of the city may force tourists away under fierce competition among tourist destinations in the world.
5. For future researchers, other Heritage Sites in Southeast Asia can be tried out in the study. furthermore, researcher can compare the assessment of local and international tourists to improve the overall services quality.
6. This developed proposed service delivery improvement plan can be beneficial in drafting guidelines, policies, rules and regulations in order to maintain, preserve and conserve the selected heritage sites. This proposed service delivery improvement plan should fully be reviewed for their timely preparation and implementation and if more time or budget can be allotted in enhancing the critical factors in the overall service quality in tourism to ensure the development procedure. It has the capability to address service quality concerns/issues on how to meet the expectation of customers while protecting the heritage sites from disruptions and introducing on-going UNESCO World Heritage Sites. However, the said system needs to be enhanced to make it more accessible to attract more users of the site.

Service Delivery Improvement Plan

Concerned Heritage Sites	Objective	Strategies/ Methodologies	Resources	Personnel involved	Success indicator
Angkor, Cambodia	Develop better tourist maps, brochures, sign boards and signages	Production of brochures, sign boards and signages	Updated Information of Heritage sites	Heritage Staffs Tourism Officers Local Government Unit	100% updated production of brochures, sign boards and signages
	Continue strengthen the training of heritage staffs and tour guides to understand the value of professionalism in the aspect of commitment, competence, compassion and caring.	Training of Heritage Staffs and tour guides	Training Design and Proposal Training Materials And Manuals	Heritage Staff Tourism Officers Department of Tourism	100% attendance to the training 100% of staffs and tour guides be able to understand the value of professionalism in the aspect of commitment, competence, compassion and caring
	Continue enhance the promotion of tourism programs and activities across social media	Enhancement or Creation of Social Media accounts and websites	Social Media and Website Account Updated and complete information of tourism programs and activities	Heritage Staff Tourism Officers	100 % enhancement promotion of tourism programs and activities

Angkor, Cambodia	Develop diversified tourism products and engage local communities	Check availability of Locally made tourism products	List of Locally made products History of Locally made products and services	Tourism Officers Local Government Unit Department of Tourism Business Permit and Licensing Office	100 % availability of locally made tourism products and other services that relate to and support the values and identity of heritage site.
	Improve Budget Planning / Implementation support for tourism related activities	Suggested tourism related activities	Budgetary plan	Tourism Officers Local Government Unit	100% collaboration with Tourism Officers and Local Government Unit for Allocate funding support
Borobudur Temple, Indonesia	Develop better tourist maps, brochures, sign boards and signages.	Production of updated information boards, maps and guides	Updated Information of Heritage sites	Heritage Staff Tourism Officers Local Government Unit	100% collaboration Tourism Officers, Local Government Unit and Department of Tourism in order to produce a tourist maps, brochures, sign boards and signages
	Allocate funding support for conservation of the stone of the Temple and other display of artifacts	Organize a meeting or conference with Tourism Officers, Local Government Unit, Department of Tourism and business groups	Budgetary plan	Tourism Officers Local Government Unit Department of Tourism	100% collaboration with Tourism Officers, Local Government Unit and Department of Tourism for regular inspection in Tourism Heritage Sites to ensure that Interior and exterior design of the historic temples are well maintained and protected.

	Develop a productive, competent and well-motivated tourism workforce	Regular inspection in Tourism Heritage Sites and Training of Heritage Staff	Inspection Policies and Guidelines Training Materials Training Manuals Policies and Guidelines	Tourism Officers Local Government Unit Department of Tourism	100% attendance to the trainings, workshops for tourism related activities 100% knowledge on how to become productive, competent and well-motivated tourism workforce
Borobudur Temple, Indonesia	Continue train heritage staff and tour guides to understand the value of professionalism in the aspect of commitment, competence, compassion and caring.	Training of Heritage Staff	Training Design and Proposal Training Materials And Manuals	Heritage Staff Tourism Officers Department of Tourism	100% attendance to the training 100% of staff and tour guides be able to understand the value of professionalism in the aspect of commitment, competence, compassion and caring
	Continue develop marketing and promotional campaigns to introduce different facilities and tourism sites.	Enhancement or Creation of Social Media accounts and websites	Social Media and Website Account Updated and complete information of tourism programs and activities	Heritage Staff Tourism Officers	100 % enhancement promotion of tourism programs and activities
Borobudur Temple, Indonesia	Intensify responsible tourist awareness	Orientation of responsible tourist awareness	Training Design, Materials And Manuals	Heritage Staffs Tourism Officers	100 % orientation of responsible tourist awareness

	intensify potential collaboration between the local community, local government and private sectors	Set up meeting/conference	Letter of request invitation and proposal	Local Community Tourism Officers Local Government Unit Private Sectors	100% collaboration between the local community, local government and private sectors
Historic City of Vigan, Philippines	Improvement of tour services, including tourist information, transportation within the district and tour guide	Voice of the customer through Customer Satisfaction Survey / Feedback in Heritage Sites Attraction	Sample Customer Satisfaction Survey Policies and Guidelines	Heritage Staff/ tour guides Tourism Officers Department of Tourism	Upgraded tour services
	Provide coaching and mentoring for staffs and tour guides on how to properly manage tourist flows and understand the value of professionalism in the aspect of commitment, competence, compassion and caring.	Training of Staffs and tour guides	Training Design and Proposal Training Materials Training Manuals Policies and Guidelines	Staffs and tour guides Tourism Officers Local Government Unit Department of Tourism	100% attendance to the program 100% knowledge on how to properly manage tourist flows 100% of staff and tour guides be able to understand the value of professionalism in the aspect of commitment, competence, compassion and caring
	Create genuine partnership, and unity with and among investors and community in order to enhance rest areas and mobility aid	Coordinate with business groups and community	Letter of request invitation and proposal	Tourism Officers Local Government Unit Department of Tourism Business Groups Community	100% coordination with investors and community

<p>Historic City of Vigan, Philippines</p>	<p>Develop diversified tourism products and engage local communities</p>	<p>Check availability of Locally made tourism products</p>	<p>List of Locally made products History of Locally made products and services</p>	<p>Tourism Officers Local Government Unit Department of Tourism Business Permit and Licensing Office</p>	<p>100 % availability of locally made tourism products and other services that relate to and support the values and identity of heritage site.</p>
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Author Information

Mary Grace H. Laserna

Centro Escolar University

9 Mendiola St, San Miguel, Manila, 1008 Metro

Manila, Philippines
